

A Study of Maternal Factors Associated with Very Low Birth Weight in Neonates

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Abstract:

Background: Birth weight is not only a critical determinant of child survival, growth and development but also a valuable indicator of maternal health, nutrition and quality of life. Low Birth Weight is closely associated with fetal and perinatal mortality and morbidity. The present study was undertaken to evaluate the maternal factors responsible for Very Low Birth Weight (VLBW) newborn.

Objective: To study the maternal factors influencing very low birth weight babies.

Design: Prospective Case Control Study.

Setting: SNCU (Inborn unit), Department of Paediatrics, Jhalawar Medical College, Jhalawar.

Participants: All Newborns delivered in SHKBM Hospital, Jhalawar medical college and admitted in SNCU (Special Newborn Care Unit) with birth weight less than 1500 Gms irrespective of gestational age over a period of one year were included in the study as cases. Healthy babies (with birth weight > 2.5 kg) which were born on same day as of case were randomly selected in ratio of 1:1 as controls.

Main Outcome Measure(s): Maternal factors taken into consideration were: Age, Parity, Birth interval, Height and Weight of the mother, Mid arm circumference, Literacy of the mother, Family structure, Mother's occupation, Per capita income, Antenatal visits, Maternal diseases during the antenatal period and Bad obstetric history. Neonatal factors taken into consideration were: weight, sex and gestational age.

Results: Out of 112 cases, 86 were preterm appropriate for gestational age, 11 were term small for gestational age and 15 were preterm small for gestational age. Maternal factors like birth intervals, maternal weight, mid arm circumference, literacy, income, antenatal visits and bad obstetric history were significantly related whereas maternal age distribution, parity, mother's height, family structure, mother's occupation and maternal diseases had no significant relation to Very Low Birth Weight in the newborns.

Conclusions: In our study, the incidence of VLBW was found to be associated with maternal factors like less birth intervals, low maternal weight, less mid arm circumference, illiteracy, low per capita income, less antenatal check-up visits and bad obstetric history. Health education and antenatal care are of utmost importance to prevent low birth weight in newborns.

Keywords: Very Low Birth Weight, Special Newborn care unit (SNCU), Small for gestational age, maternal factors.

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Introduction

Low birth weight (LBW) is defined as a birth weight below 2500 gms regardless of gestational age and is usually applied to live births only. LBW includes both appropriately grown preterm neonates (<37 completed weeks of gestation) and term and preterm growth-restricted neonates (<10th centile of weight for gestational age and sex) but remains an important public health indicator, especially in settings where accurate gestational age assessment is not possible [1]. World Health Organization (WHO) defined low birth weight as weight at birth of less than 2500 gms regardless of gestational age. This cut-off point is based on observations that newborns weighing less than 2500 gms are 20 times more likely to die than

heavier babies. LBW can be further subcategorized as very low birth weight (VLBW), which is less than 1500 gms and extremely low birth weight (ELBW), which is less than 1000 gms [2]. In developed countries the incidence of low birth weight is less than 10% whereas in developing countries it is in the range of 15-30% of the total birth. In India about 30% of babies born are of low birth weight. Out of this 30%, 10% is due to preterm deliveries and the remaining is due to Intrauterine Growth Retardation [3]. Every fourth baby in India is low birth weight baby accounting for a high load of morbidity and mortality [4]. LBW is the major risk factor for infant morbidity and mortality, (36% of all mortality in children <5 yrs

of age), constituting about 4 million deaths per year. Hence low birth weight is considered as a sensitive index of nation's health and development. Reducing the incidence of low birth weight is one of the most serious challenges in maternal and child health in developing countries [5].

Birth weight is not only a critical determinant of child survival, growth and development but also a valuable indicator of maternal health, nutrition and quality of life. The present study was undertaken to evaluate the maternal factors responsible for Very Low Birth Weight newborn.

Materials & Methods

This Prospective Case Control Study was carried out in Department of Paediatrics at Jhalawar medical college and attached Shrimati Heera Kunwar Baa Mahila (SHKBM) Hospital, Jhalawar, Rajasthan over a period of 15 months from Jan, 2022 to March, 2023 (Data collection period – 12 months & Data analysis period – 3 months). An ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee.

Inclusion Criteria

The study included all newborns delivered in Shrimati Heera Kunwar Baa Mahila Hospital and admitted in Special Newborn Care Unit (SNCU) with birth weight less than 1500 gms irrespective of gestational age during the study period. The parent of the cases were duly informed, explained about the study and consent was taken. Healthy newborns (with birth weight > 2.5 kg) which were born on same day as of case were randomly selected in ratio of 1:1 and enrolled as controls.

Exclusion criteria

1. Multiple pregnancies.
2. Still births.
3. Outborn babies.
4. Newborns with major congenital anomalies and syndromes.

Sampling technique:

For cases: Complete enumeration (Census).

For controls: Simple random sampling.

Data collection

All neonates delivered in Shrimati Heera Kunwar Baa Mahila Hospital and admitted in SNCU (Special Newborn Care Unit) during the study

period, who fulfill the inclusion criteria were included in the study as cases.

In control group, an equal number of newborns of weight more than or equal to 2500 gms selected by simple randomized technique born on the very same day of the selection of the cases were included.

Maternal factors which were taken into consideration were: Age, Parity, Birth interval, Height of the mother, Weight of the mother, Mid arm circumference, Literacy of the mother, Family structure, Mother's occupation, Per capita income per month, Antenatal visits, Maternal diseases during the antenatal period and Bad obstetric history.

Neonatal factors which were taken into consideration were: Weight of the newborn, Sex of the newborn and Gestational age of newborn. In this study, assessment of gestational age of newborns was done using New Ballard Scoring system.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was done by SPSS software (23.0 trial version) and appropriate statistical tests were used for finding the final results. To describe nominal data, simple percentage was used. Chi-square test was applied to determine the association between different variations where ever possible.

Results

A total number of 128 newborns with birth weight less than 1500 gms were admitted in SNCU during the study period of one year. Out of these 128 VLBW newborns, 16 newborns were excluded based on exclusion criteria and only 112 cases were included in the study. 112 healthy newborns (with birth weight > 2.5 kg) which were born on same day as of case were randomly selected in ratio of 1:1 and were enrolled as controls. Table no. 1 mentions the neonatal factors in relation to birth weight. Among the case group, out of 112 cases, 86 were preterm appropriate for gestational age, 11 were term small for gestational age and 15 were preterm small for gestational age. In control group all the newborns were full term normal birth weight babies. The gender of the baby had no significant effect on the birth weight.

Table 1:

Neonatal Factors	VLBW group n(%)	NBW group n (%)	Total n (%)	P Value
Gestational maturity				
Preterm AGA	86 (100)	0 (0)	86 (100)	
Term SGA	11 (100)	0 (0)	11 (100)	
Preterm SGA	15 (100)	0 (0)	15 (100)	
Term AGA	0 (0)	112 (100)	112 (100)	

Total	112	112	224	
Sex				
Male	51 (47)	57 (53)	108 (100)	P =0.4224
Female	61 (52)	55 (48)	116 (100)	
Total	112	112	224	

Case group subjects (mothers) were those who delivered VLBW babies (<1.5 kg) while the control group subjects (mothers) had delivered normal birth weight babies (>2.5 kg). Table No. 2 presents the maternal factors in relation to birth weight of the babies. Both the groups were found to statistically comparable ($p>0.05$) as per maternal age distribution, parity, mother's height, family structure, mother's occupation and maternal diseases meaning that there is no significant effect of these factors on birth weight.

A significant difference was observed among the two groups when compared for birth interval. Among the cases, most of them were primi mothers with <2 yrs birth intervals (85/112). Only 27 mothers in case group had birth interval >2 yrs suggesting that if the birth interval is less, there are more chances of VLBW deliveries ($p=0.0012$).

It was found that the incidence of very low birth weight babies was higher in mothers with lower weight and poor nutritional status and the differences were found to be statistically significant. Among controls, only 8 subjects had <40 kg weight while among cases, 37 subjects had <40 kg of weight, proving to be contributing to VLBW condition ($p=0.001$).

A significant difference was also observed among the two groups when compared for mothers mid arm circumference (representing nutritional status). Among controls, most subjects had >21 cm of MAC whereas 26 subjects among cases had MAC

of <21 cm representing malnutrition, proving to be contributing to VLBW condition ($p=0.0065$). Among control group, majority of the subjects had >5 antenatal visits, only 4 out of 112 subjects had <3 antenatal visits. Whereas in the case group, 14 had <3 antenatal visits, 41 had 3-5 visits and 57 had >5 visits. There was a statistically significant difference as per antenatal visits among both the groups. Thus, less antenatal visits also contribute to VLBW deliveries ($p=0.0149$).

Furthermore, significant differences were also observed among the two groups when compared for mother's literacy status and per capita income. 36 mothers among the cases were found to be illiterate as compared to only 15 illiterate mothers in control group ($p=0.0034$) proving the importance of education in preventing low birth weight in newborns.

Also only 23 subjects out of 112 in control group had <1000/- of per capita income whereas 45 subjects in cases had <1000/- of per capita income, proving it to be contributing to VLBW condition ($p=0.0039$).

Bad Obstetric History (BOH) was observed more among the mothers of case group. 35 cases had mothers with bad obstetric history while only 14 controls had the same. This difference was found to be statistically highly significant ($p=0.007$) meaning that, bad obstetric history contributes to VLBW deliveries.

Table 2:

Maternal Factors	VLBW group n (%)	NBW group n (%)	Total n (%)	P Value
Age (in years)				
<20 years	25 (66)	13 (34)	38 (100)	P =0.1021
21-30 years	80 (47)	80 (47)	171 (100)	
21-30 years	7 (47)	8 (53)	15 (100)	
Total	112	112	224	
Gravida				
Primi	43 (57)	33 (43)	76 (100)	P =0.3695
2 and 3	62 (47)	71 (53)	133 (100)	
>3	7 (47)	8 (53)	8 (53)	
Total	112	112	224	
Birth interval				
<2 years	42 (62)	26 (38)	68 (100)	P =0.0012
>2 years	27 (34)	53 (66)	80 (100)	
Total	69	79	148	
Mother's height				
≤140 cm	10 (59)	7 (41)	17 (100)	P =0.7129
141-149 cm	29 (47)	32 (53)	61 (100)	
≥150 cm	73 (50)	73 (50)	146 (100)	

Total	112	112	224	
Mother's weight				
≤40 kg	37 (82)	8 (18)	45 (100)	P =0.7129
41-49 kg	41 (45)	51 (55)	92 (100)	
≥50 kg	34 (35)	53 (65)	87 (100)	
Total	112	112	224	
Mid arm circumference				
≤20 cm	26 (74)	9 (26)	35 (100)	P =0.0065
21-22 cm	40 (48)	44 (52)	84 (100)	
>22 cm	46 (44)	59 (56)	105 (100)	
Total	112	112	224	
Mothers literacy				
Illiterate	36 (71)	15 (29)	51 (100)	P =0.0034
Prim. and middle school	51 (43)	68 (57)	119 (100)	
High school &above	25 (46)	29 (54)	54 (100)	
Total	112	112	224	
Per capita income				
< 1000	45 (66)	23(34)	68(100)	P =0.0039
1000-1499	41 (40)	61(60)	102(100)	
≥1500	26 (48)	28(52)	54 (100)	
Total	112	112	224	
Family structure				
Nuclear	48 (44)	61 (56)	109 (100)	P =0.0822
Joint	64 (56)	51 (44)	115 (100)	
Total	112	112	224	
Maternal occupation				
Housewife	79 (51)	75 (49)	154 (100)	P =0.6364
Light work	25 (50)	25 (50)	50 (100)	
Heavy work	8 (40)	12 (60)	20 (100)	
Total	112	112	224	
Antenatal visits				
<3 visits	14 (78)	4 (22)	18 (100)	P =0.0149
3-5 visits	41 (55)	34 (45)	75 (100)	
>5 visits	57 (43)	74 (57)	131 (100)	
Total	112 (100)	112 (100)	224	
Maternal disease				
No disease	39 (45)	48 (55)	87 (100)	P =0.738
PIH	33 (58)	24 (42)	57 (100)	
Anemia	16 (44)	20 (56)	36 (100)	
APH	9 (64)	05 (36)	14 (100)	
Others	15 (50)	15 (50)	30 (100)	
Total	112	112	224	
Bad obstetric history				
Present	35 (71)	14 (29)	49 (100)	P=0.0007
Absent	77 (44)	98 (56)	175 (100)	
Total	112	112	224	

Discussion

This study was a hospital based prospective case control study, conducted over a period of 15 months at a tertiary care centre with well-equipped facilities, which included 112 newborns in each group as cases (birth weight <1500 gms) and controls (normal birth weight) with their mothers as subjects. Both groups were evaluated and compared based on the various neonatal and maternal factors. In our study, BOH (Bad obstetric history) was observed more among the subjects of case

group. 31.2% cases had bad obstetric history while only 12.5% controls had the same. This difference was found to be statistically highly significant ($p=0.007$).

This infers that BOH contributes to VLBW deliveries. This is supported by the studies like, Meresa et al[6] in which 18.8% had BOH, Singh et al[7] which observed that gestational diabetes, hypothyroid, malpresentations, hypertension, fetal distress, premature deliveries were the common causes of bad obstetric history in pregnant mothers

and Anu MS et al[8] which also observed that an association existed between bad obstetric history and birth weight of the newborn ($p < 0.001$).

A significant difference was observed among the two groups when compared for per capita incomes proving it to be contributing to VLBW condition in the present study. This is in akin to the study done by Anu MS et al[8] where an association existed between the maternal income and birth weight of the new born ($p < 0.001$). But in our study, maternal occupation was not found to be significantly associated with birth weight of the babies which is in contradiction to the study done by Anu MS et al[8] where an association also existed between the maternal occupation and birth weight of the newborn ($p < 0.001$).

The mean Height and weight of pregnant women included in the study by Anu MS et al[8] was observed to be 62.94 ± 10.09 kg and 160.1 ± 7.15 cm respectively and it was observed that a significant association existed between the maternal height and weight with birth weight of the new born ($p < 0.001$).

Whereas in our study a significant difference was observed among the two groups when compared for mother's weight but mother's height was found to be statistically similar in both the groups. These observations were in accordance with the study by Arati Deka et al[9] where a significant association existed between the maternal weight with birth weight of the new born ($p < 0.0016$) and no association between maternal height and birth weight of the baby was observed ($p > 0.05$).

Maternal Age and Birth weight of the new born were not found to be significantly associated with each other in the present study. This is in contradiction to the study done by Arati Deka et al[9] and Anu MS et al[8] where a significant association between maternal age and birth weight of the baby was observed.

We also observed a significant difference ($p = 0.0012$) among the two groups when compared for birth interval meaning that, if the birth interval is less, there are more chances of VLBW deliveries. Mother's mid arm circumference (representing nutritional status) and mother's literacy status were also found to have a significant association with birth weight of newborns.

Conclusion

Our study concludes that maternal factors like less birth intervals, low maternal weight, less mid arm circumference, illiteracy, low per capita income, less antenatal check-up visits and bad obstetric history are significantly related to Very Low Birth Weight in the newborns. Thus health education, antenatal counselling and nutritional care during pregnancy along with proper implementation of health programmes are essential to prevent low birth weight among newborns.

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